

INFLUENCE OF FRICTION ON THE SURFACE CHARACTERISTICS OF EPDM ELASTOMERS WITH DIFFERENT CARBON BLACK CONTENTS

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ABSTRACT

Tribological properties and surface characteristics of ethylene–propylene–diene elastomers were studied as a function of carbon black (CB) content. The surface analysis was performed inside and outside the wear track by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) in order to evaluate possible compositional changes produced by rubbing. Carbon black content had only a small influence on the surface chemistry of the unworn surfaces. However, on the surfaces subjected to friction, the oxygen concentration decreased with increasing CB content. Neither the surface analysis by XPS nor the wettability tests revealed important thermal degradation of the polymer in these friction tests.

HIGHLIGHTS

- ▶ Oxygen on the EPDM surface is related with additives and not with backbone of the polymer.
- ▶ Zinc segregates on the friction surface depends on the carbon black content.
- ▶ Intrinsic water contact angle increases on the friction zone.
- ▶ No degradation and oxidation of the backbone structure were observed under these test conditions.

KEYWORDS

Surface analysis; ; EPDM; Dry sliding; Wettability

1. INTRODUCTION

Ethylene–propylene–diene monomer rubber (EPDM) is one of the synthetic ethylene–propylene rubbers, the use of which is rapidly growing in different applications such as waterproof coatings, rubber contact switches, floor heating, electromagnetic interference shielding, various electronic and electrical applications, sidewalls, cover strips, wires, sporting goods, outdoor electrical insulators and in a variety of automotive applications (41% of worldwide use) [1], [2], [3], [4]. These applications usually demand a material

with good mechanical properties and with a retained elastic nature. Another important property of EPDM is good resistance to degradation at elevated temperature, light, in oxygen and, in particular, ozone [5].

The mechanical, physical, chemical and tribological properties of EPDM depend not only on the molecular weight of the polymer, but also on the reinforcing filler [6], [7], [8], [9]. The distribution of the filler in the blend, the filler dispersion in each phase and the chemical interactions between the polymer and the filler [6] have a significant influence on the performance of the rubber. One of the most widely used fillers is carbon black (CB), because it improves the stiffness and the toughness of rubber [4], while maintaining high flexibility and good physical and mechanical properties of the rubber at low manufacturing costs.

In previous studies, Felhös and Karger-Kocsis [10] and Karger-Kocsis et al. [11] studied friction and wear behaviour of EPDM against steel as a function of CB content using different test configurations. They observed that the unfilled EPDM failed by massive material detachment in small fragments, which were partially agglomerated due to the low tensile and tear strength of this EPDM. Incorporation of CB changed the wear mechanism fundamentally, such that a Schallamach-type wavy pattern appeared. By increasing the CB content, the size of the Schallamach waves decreased and the overall surface showed some smearing. In addition, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis at high magnification revealed formation of fibrils. Karger-Kocsis et al. [11] speculated that both effects, smearing and fibril formation, were due to tribochemical reactions and thermooxidative degradation of the EPDM. However, no satisfactory arguments for these chemical mechanisms were presented.

In order to provide insight into the mechanisms of EPDM failure, in this work we studied the surface characteristics of EPDM before and after friction by means of X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (XPS), white light confocal microscopy, SEM and sessile drop contact angle measurements.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1. Materials

Samples of ethylene–propylene–diene rubber were prepared in a laboratory internal mixer. The curatives were introduced using a laboratory open mill. The recipe used in parts per hundred rubber (phr) was EPDM (Keltan® 512 of DSM Elastomers, Sittard, The Netherlands): 100 parts; carbon black (N550): 0, 30, 45 and 60 parts; ZnO: 5 parts; N-cyclohexyl-2-benzothiazole sulphenamide (CBS, Vulkacit CZ of Bayer, Leverkusen, Germany): 0.6 parts; 2-mercapto benzothiazole (MBT, Vulkacit Mercapto by Bayer): 0.6 parts; zinc dibenzyl dithiocarbamate (Rhenogran ZBEC-70 of Rhein Chemie): 1.5 parts; zinc dicyanatodiamine (Rhenogran Geniplex 80 of Rhein Chemie, Mannheim, Germany): 0.6 parts.

2.2. Tribological characterisation

Tribological characteristics of the samples, i.e., friction coefficient and loss volume due to wear, were tested using a SOP 3000 tribotester from Dr. Tillwich GmbH (Horb-Ahldorf, Germany) with a roller (steel)-on-plate (rubber) (ROP) configuration (Fig. 1). Rubber samples had the following dimensions: 4 mm×12 mm×8 mm. The standard counter body was a cylinder with a diameter of 10 mm fabricated from 9SMnPb28k steel according to the DIN7 standard and was provided by Dr. Tillwich GmbH. Surface roughness, R_a , of the counter body was 0.9 μm . Geometry, material and surface roughness of the counter body were standard parameters for this type of test. Sliding speed, V_{fr} , was 250 mm/s, normal load, F_N , was 12 N, contact length between the sample and the roller, L , was 8 mm and the test duration, Δt , was 90 min. These experimental conditions were within the range of normal load and sliding speed used by Karger-Kocsis et al. in their work [11]. Normal load and tangential force, F_T , were measured and registered during friction. Before the tests, the rubber specimen and the counter body were cleaned in an isopropanol bath. For each particular test condition at least 5 tests were carried out to obtain average values of the coefficient of friction and loss volume due to wear.

2.3. X-ray photoemission spectroscopy

The XPS measurements of the samples after the tribotest were performed inside and outside the wear track in an ultra-high-vacuum (UHV) chamber with a base pressure of 1×10^{-10} mbar. The angle between the hemispherical analyser (Specs-PHOIBOS100) and the plane of the surface was 60° . An X-ray radiation source with the $\text{MgK}\alpha$ line (1253.6 eV) was used. The survey spectra were obtained with a photon energy step of 0.25 eV and pass energy of 40 eV. Additionally, the C 1s core levels were measured with a photon energy step of 0.1 eV and pass energy of 15 eV. Before the analysis of the obtained data, the contribution of the $\text{MgK}\alpha$ satellite line was subtracted and the spectra were subjected to a Shirley background subtraction formalism. The binding energy (BE) scale was calibrated with respect to the C 1s peak at 285 eV. In order to remove atmospheric contamination from the sample surfaces, they were sputtered with Ar^+ ions using an ion gun at an ion energy of 1.4 keV and beam current of 0.2 μA for 15 min. The analysed surface area for the XPS was approximately 5.6 mm^2 , which is large enough to obtain the average chemical composition of the surface.

2.4. Wettability tests

The wettability tests were performed after the XPS measurements on the same samples, in order to be sure that changes observed in the EPDM samples with the different techniques employed could be correlated. Contact angle (CA) measurements were carried out by a sessile drop method using drops of 4 μl of deionised water at room temperature. The surface energy evaluation system (SEE) [12] was used for the acquisition of the drop images and measurement of CA. Two sets of at least four repeated CA measurements were performed on each region of the samples: on the unworn surface and on the wear track. Then, the mean value and standard error of the mean (SE) were determined from these measurements. Roughness correction of the measured CA was done using the Wenzel approach [13], [14]. For this purpose, three-dimensional surface images were obtained using white light confocal microscopy with a 20 \times objective. Then, the surface

roughness ratio, i.e., the ratio of the actual surface area to the projected surface area, was calculated from these images using an algorithm developed and published elsewhere [15].

2.5. Microscopy

Surface morphology and surface chemical composition of the rubber samples in the friction zone were studied using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) on a Nova™ NanoSEM 230 equipped with a field emission gun (FE), an energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDX-EDAX) and a low voltage high contrast detector (vCD). Samples were characterised in low vacuum without additional metallising. Point analysis, line scans and spectral mapping were used with the aim to identify the spatial distribution of the elements. The image size used for determination of the elemental composition in the EDX analysis was $108 \times 86 \mu\text{m}^2$.

In addition, in order to evaluate the roughness factor of the friction zones of the EPDM samples, 3D surface morphology was characterised using a confocal white light microscope NIKON Eclipse EM600, equipped with a scanning system, Pi piezo Prior, and a $20\times$ objective. Images $1.31 \times 0.96 \text{ mm}^2$ in size were taken and analysed using the Plμ Confocal Imaging Profiler 1.7 software.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Tribological tests

Fig. 2 shows the friction coefficient (COF) and loss volume due to wear of EPDM elastomers with various CB contents. The COF was determined as the ratio of the tangential force to the normal load in a steady friction regime. This parameter was almost independent of the CB content for all EPDM samples and had a mean value of about 1.5.

Earlier, Karger-Kocsis et al. [11] observed different COF behaviours of EPDM with varying CB content depending on the test configuration. In experiments with ROP configuration, like the one used in this work, COF decreased as CB content increased. However, when the pin-on-plane (POP) configuration with circular motion was used, the COF did not change with the CB content. A rough estimation of the contact stress showed that the maximal contact stress in our experiments was 3–4.2 times higher than in the ROP tests in [11], but 31–40 times lower than in their POP tests. Therefore, it seems that the behaviour of COF may depend on the contact stress and/or the stress gradient on the contact zone: for higher contact stress and/or larger stress gradients, the COF does not change with CB content, while for lower contact stress and/or smaller stress gradients, the COF decreases with increasing CB content. In general, it is known that for polymers COF decreases with increase in the contact stress [16]. Since for the same normal load the contact stress is higher for harder EPDMs, which contain larger amount of CB, COF should decrease with increasing CB content. This is the case for the ROP tests in [11], but not for our tests. We suppose that this disparity could be attributed to different stress distribution in the contact zones resulted from different roller diameters in [11] and in our tests, since a reasonable suggestion is that COF depends on the local contact stress rather than on its maximum value. Further experimental studies and modelling are necessary to elucidate the dependence of COF on contact stress distribution.

The loss volume was calculated based on the measured width and depth of the wear tracks, assuming an elliptical shape of the wear track cross-section. The wear rate significantly decreased with increasing CB content: the difference in loss volume between the EPDM samples without CB and the samples with 60 phr of CB exceeded two orders of magnitude (Fig. 2, note the logarithmic scale). These findings are consistent with the results presented in [11].

Wear mechanisms were analysed using optical, white light confocal and scanning electron microscopies. The surface structures observed on the samples after the friction tests are shown in Fig. 3. The samples without CB (Fig. 3a) had a rough surface with massive material removal due to the low tensile strength. CB incorporation to EPDM promoted the formation of Schallamach waves. With increasing CB content, thicker ridges appeared on the surface, while the period of the Schallamach waves and the amount of wear debris decreased. This evolution of the abrasion pattern revealed that increasing amounts of CB gradually avoided delamination of EPDM with rupture of the tongues formed due to tensile stress. The sharper top of the tongues can be related with loss of material due to tear [16] and, therefore, the rounded shape of EPDM with higher CB incorporation evidenced better wear performance for this material. This wear behaviour was consistent with previously published results [11]; however, no evidence of any fibrillar network was found in the analysis of our surfaces at various magnifications up to 7000× (Fig. 3e–h). Even though the results of the temperature measurements were not reported in [11], the authors speculated that the fibrillar microstructure could be traced to tribochemical effects due to the important temperature increase in the contact zone. In order to check this hypothesis, we calculated the flash temperature in the contact zone between EPDM and a steel roller for the experimental conditions of our tests using Tian and Kennedy's simple model [17]:

$$T_{max} = \frac{2F_N \mu V_{fr}}{L \sqrt{\pi} (\lambda_1 \sqrt{1 + Pe_1} + \lambda_2 \sqrt{1 + Pe_2})} \quad (1)$$

where μ is the COF, λ_1 and λ_2 are the thermal conductivities of EPDM and steel, respectively, and Pe_1 and Pe_2 are the Péclet numbers for EPDM and steel, respectively.

The Péclet number is defined as:

$$Pe_i = \frac{V_i b \rho_i C_{pi}}{4 \lambda_i} \quad (2)$$

where V_i is the velocity of the i th part, b is the width of the linear contact along sliding direction, ρ_i is the density and C_{pi} is the specific heat at constant pressure.

For EPDM $V_1=0$ and, thus, $Pe_1=0$. Therefore (1) can be simplified as:(3)

$$T_{max} = \frac{2F_N \mu V_{fr}}{L \sqrt{\pi} (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 \sqrt{1 + Pe_2})} \quad (3)$$

The following parameters were used for the calculation of the flash temperature: $\lambda_1=0.25 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, $\lambda_2=47 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, $\rho_1=103 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $\rho_2=7.8 \times 10^3 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $C_{p1}=103 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [18], [19], $C_{p2}=5 \times 10^2 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $b=2\text{--}4 \text{ mm}$ (the highest value corresponds to the unfilled EPDM). The flash temperature in the contact zone determined from (3) ranged between 2.89 and 5.79 °C, depending on b . These values were much lower than the temperature required for the expected thermochemical and thermooxidative effects.

Expressions (1), (3) can only be used for the determination of flash temperature over the mean surface temperature. Undoubtedly, with prolonged friction, the mean surface temperature will also increase due to frictional heat absorption by the EPDM and the steel roller. However, the increase in mean surface temperature is a function of many factors such as heat dissipation in the air due to conductivity and convection or heat conductivity through the holder. These factors are difficult to control and to model; therefore, we assumed the temperature increase due to frictional heat absorption in adiabatic conditions as an upper bound of the mean temperature increase:

$$\Delta T_{mean}^{up} = \sigma \frac{F_N \mu V_{fr} \Delta t}{C_{p1} V_{s1} \rho_1} \quad (4)$$

where V_{s1} is the volume of the sample and σ is the heat partition function, which is defined as follows [17]:

$$\sigma = \frac{\lambda_1 \sqrt{1 + Pe_1}}{\lambda_1 \sqrt{1 + Pe_1} + \lambda_2 \sqrt{1 + Pe_2}} \quad (5)$$

For our experimental conditions, the heat partition function was $\sigma=1.14 \times 10^{-3}$ and the upper bound of the mean temperature increase was $\Delta T_{mean}^{up} = 72\text{--}99 \text{ °C}$, depending on b . The latter was probably overestimated from 30% to 50%. The upper bound of the absolute maximum temperature in the contact region was determined as the sum of the ambient temperature, the increase in the mean temperature and flash temperature that in our case ranged between 100 and 130 °C (for an ambient temperature of 25 °C). By taking into account convection and heat conductivity, the real values should be between 22 and 50 °C lower and, therefore, below 110 °C. From the viewpoint of the thermochemistry of EPDM, this temperature is not high enough either, especially with the relatively short test duration, i.e. 90 min, as reported recently [13]. However, these values are close to the limit of thermal stability of EPDM (about 150 °C).

Similarly, we estimated the flash temperature and mean temperature increase from the experimental conditions reported in [11]. The corresponding values were $T_{max \text{ k-k}}=0.51\text{--}1.62 \text{ °C}$ and $\Delta T_{mean, \text{ k-k}}^{up} = 12.1\text{--}29.0 \text{ °C}$. Thus, the upper bound of the absolute temperature should be in the range of 37.6–55.6 °C. These values are smaller than those in the present work because of the relatively lower contact pressure used in [11].

The coarse estimation of the temperatures in the contact zone performed in this work highlighted that while thermal effects may contribute to mechanical and rheological changes to the properties of EPDM, i.e. related to deformation and flow, [20], it does not appear to be the main cause for tribochemical reactions. Also, we supposed that the difference in the composition of the roller material (9SMnPb28k in our work vs. 100Cr6

in [11]) was not a determining factor for the absence of fibrillar structures since none of the alloying elements of the roller were detected in the chemical analysis of the EPDM surface as we present below. In the following sections, the results obtained for the surface chemical characterisation and wettability measurements are presented pursuing the goal of a deeper understanding of possible chemical modifications to EPDM under friction.

3.2. Chemical surface characterisation of the samples

Fig. 4 presents the surface chemical composition (%) of the samples outside (left) and inside (right) the contact zones, obtained after the removal of contamination from the surface. Irrespective of the CB content, carbon was the main component of the surface coming from the elastomer backbone structure. Small amounts of other elements like O, Si, S, N and Zn arising from the additives were also detected. The atomic concentrations of elements other than carbon remained below 5%. The elements with concentrations below 0.25% are not shown in the graph.

An increase in the oxygen concentration and its bonding to carbon atoms in the friction zone are expected if some thermooxidation processes and tribochemical reactions occur [21]. However, two different tendencies were observed as far as the amount of oxygen in the friction zone is concerned. For unfilled EPDM, the amount of oxygen on the surface increased after the friction tests, whereas when CB was present, the oxygen content decreased in the wear track. Fig. 5 displays the O 1s (a) and C 1s (b) core level peaks of the samples out of the wear track. The overlap of the O 1s spectra evidenced no changes in the BE of the oxygen present on the samples as a function of the CB content. The same trend was observed in the C 1s spectra where all samples presented similar shapes irrespective of the CB content (Fig. 5b), with a single contribution at 285 eV from the C–C/C–H component (see inset) that reflects the absence of oxygen-containing functional groups (C–O bonds at 286.4 eV, C=O at 287.9 eV or O–C=O at 289.1 eV [22], [23], [24]).

The analysis of the friction zone (Fig. 5c) also presented a similar shape of the oxygen peak, and only a slight broadening at lower BE of the EPDM 0 and 30 phr spectra could be observed. On the other hand, in the analysis of the C 1s core level peaks (Fig. 5d) a wider full width at half maximum (FWHM) in the same samples could also be observed. The cause for this increase in the FWHM could be initially attributed to the rougher wear track of these samples. However, an equivalent variation in FWHM should occur in the O 1s peak, and it was not the case. Moreover, the broadening was not completely symmetric since it was slightly higher at lower BE. The fitting of the spectra with a single component of the same FWHM for all samples evidenced this asymmetry (Fig. 5d) at energies close to sp² carbon [22], [23], [24], thus suggesting the formation of double bonds in the elastomer chains of the samples with lower wear performance (EPDM 0 and 30 phr). Only for EPDM 0 phr, a small mismatch between the fitting and the experimental data could be observed at higher BE than C–C bonds. This sample presented the highest loss volume and the roughest wear track after the tribological test, which probably caused this small difference in comparison with the other samples. Even in the hypothetical case that this mismatch was caused by C–O bonds, the amount of these species would be rather small. What is clear from these fittings is the absence of carbon–oxygen bonds in the wear track that could explain the different performance in response to friction of the EPDM samples.

Elastomer degradation is usually associated with bond scission and oxidation of the backbone structure of the elastomer [16], [25]. Absence of these bonds suggests that the oxygen detected on the samples came from the additives and not from the EPDM. This conclusion was supported by the fact that silicon was found at the characteristic binding energy of its oxide form (102 eV). Other authors have suggested that fracture of macromolecular chains occurs and smaller molecular products as well as C=C structures are formed in worn surfaces [16], [26]. For the samples with larger amounts of CB (45 and 60 phr), the bond scission was smaller as can be inferred from their better wear performance; so the formation of C=C could not be appreciated with the given resolution of the XPS using a non-monochromatic lamp. Thus, chemical modification of the EPDM surface is due to mechanochemical effects rather than a thermooxidative effect [27].

The presence of CB causes a decrease in the amount of elements coming from additives (those different from carbon) inside the wear track. Furthermore, a progressive decrease in the amount of oxygen was found with increasing CB content. Oxygen is mainly associated with silicon, as found in the unworn region. In addition to this, some changes occurred in the sulphur spectrum (not shown). The as-received samples presented two peaks at about 162 and 168.5 eV: the first one is related to the S²⁻ sulphur state, while the second one is related to higher oxidation states. After the removal of air-borne contamination, there was also a significant decrease in the peak at 168.5 eV, indicating superficial localisation of these oxides and the predominant S²⁻ state in the wear track. Therefore, it seems that the sulphur chemical state at the surface of the EPDM samples was altered in the ROP tests, and a part of the oxides located in the outer surface of the elastomer was removed. However, with the XPS measurements, we obtained the average composition of the total observed area.

In addition, careful exploration of the worn surfaces using SEM and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) revealed a non-uniform distribution of zinc along the sliding direction. Fig. 6 shows SEM images of the friction zone at 500× magnification for unfilled EPDM along the sliding direction (from top to bottom). The limits of the friction zone are marked with dashed lines. On the leading edge of the specimens (Fig. 6a–c), the surface was rough, with large valleys produced by tearing of the material. On the trailing edge of the specimen, the surface was smoother with a marked wavy structure (Fig. 6d and e). The valleys on the leading edge of the specimens (Fig. 6a–c) presented some adhered debris and large bright regions. Such surface morphology is typical for rubbers and soft polymers [28], [29]. The chemical composition of the dark and bright regions obtained using EDX is presented in Table 1. This technique is spatially resolved, whereas standard XPS is not. The zinc concentration in the bright regions was 17 times greater than in the dark regions corresponding to the base polymer. Oxygen and silicon concentrations were also much higher in the bright regions than in the dark ones. With increasing CB content, the density of the bright regions decreased and white particles were dispersed more uniformly over the friction zone, although with a higher concentration at the leading edge of the specimen. On the basis of the chemical composition, these particles can be identified as a mixture of zinc oxide and silicon oxide. Zinc oxide is a vulcanisation agent in the elastomer composition. Also, some zinc oxide and other zinc compounds can be formed during friction by partial oxidation of the vulcanisation accelerators (zinc

dibenzyl dithiocarbamate and zinc dicyanatodiamine). Segregation of these particles on the surface of the friction zone, mostly at the leading edge, can be related to different wear processes occurring at the friction zone. At the leading edge, debris is formed due to tearing and fracture of the tongues. This debris rolls at the confined interface towards the trailing edge where it leaves the friction zone. During rolling, the debris is intensively deformed and oxide particles from the debris can stick to the rubber and remain in the valleys. On the other hand, at the trailing edge, there are no valleys where the oxide particles can accumulate. This can explain the non-uniform distribution of the oxides along the sliding direction. For the unfilled EPDM, the absolute concentration of zinc oxide was higher than for filled elastomers, since the composition is expressed with respect to the rubber and not to the final blend. Thus, the concentration of zinc oxide decreases with increasing CB content. In addition, there are two more factors influencing the decrease in the oxide particle concentration in the friction zone with increasing CB content: a decrease in wear rate and a change in surface morphology. Since debris is considered here as a source of oxide particles, the decrease in wear rate led to the observed reduction in the total amount of oxide particles involved in the wear and deformation processes. On the other hand, the enhancement of the tensile strength and hardness of EPDM with increasing CB content was accompanied by a continuous reduction in the valley's size at the leading edge of the friction zone, yielding fewer places where the particles can hold onto the surface.

In summary, the changes observed in terms of the surface chemical composition of the friction zone are related to the mechanical rupture of bonds and mechanical activation of the material [27] rather than to the thermochemical processes.

3.3. Contact angle measurements

The degradation of the backbone structure of elastomers commonly results in the formation of polar groups (mainly oxygen functional groups) on the surface of the wear track. Water contact angles on worn ($\theta_{fr,a}$) and untouched (θ_{nfr}) surfaces were measured to study the changes in wettability caused by the presence of new superficial functional groups. Subscript a denotes the apparent contact angle, i.e., the contact angle measured on a rough surface, which is different from the intrinsic contact angle, i.e., the contact angle on a smooth surface of the same material. Intrinsic CAs were calculated using Wenzel's approach:(6)

$$\cos \theta_{fr} = \frac{\cos \theta_{fr,a}}{r} \quad (6)$$

where r is the roughness ratio.

The values of r and θ_{fr} are shown in Table 2. As the untouched surface was smooth, the roughness correction was not applied. No significant variations in the CA of the samples were observed on the unworn surfaces, with a mean value of around 84° . Comparison of the intrinsic CA on the worn surfaces with the CA on the untouched surface was carried out for each sample using the ANOVA statistical method. The corresponding p-values and statistical power are shown in Table 2. For all samples, the CA in the friction zone was larger than on the untouched surfaces, even after roughness correction, and this

difference was statistically significant (at the significance level 0.05). These results imply that the worn surfaces were more hydrophobic than the initial ones. In a previous study [15] in which a commercial EPDM (52.6 phr) was aged at a certain temperature, a decrease in the water CA close to 50% was observed. This decrease was caused by thermooxidation of the EPDM surfaces. An outer layer dominated by methyl groups ($-\text{CH}_3$) possesses hydrophobic properties, while an arrangement of polar oxygen functional groups ($-\text{C}-\text{OH}$, $-\text{C}=\text{O}$) on the outer layer induces better wettability of polar liquids such as water [15], [30]. Therefore, the presence of new oxygen functional groups on aged EPDM caused the decrease in the water CA. In our case, no oxidation of the elastomer backbone could be observed after the XPS analysis that could cause this tendency. Furthermore, the increase in water CA observed in the wear track could be associated with the changes in the amount of additives present on the surface. The reported increase in zinc oxide and silica at the surface, which have hydrophobic and superhydrophobic properties [31], could contribute to the increased water CA in the friction zone.

4. CONCLUSIONS

XPS measurements were carried out on EPDM elastomers with different CB contents in order to establish whether there is a relationship between chemical modification of the elastomer composition and changes in the wear mechanism. The main conclusion of this work is that no thermooxidation processes as a consequence of the friction tests were observed on the EPDM, irrespective of the CB content. It was found that CB enhanced the presence of elements other than carbon in the EPDM composition. For EPDM containing CB, the wear track presented a lower oxygen content in comparison to the unworn region. This oxygen reduction was more pronounced with increasing CB content. In the case of the sample without CB, the tribological tests caused an increment in the oxygen content. The analysis of the C 1s core level revealed that the oxidation of the backbone structure of the EPDM was not the reason for the increment of oxygen in the wear track, since no carbon–oxygen bonds could be asserted after XPS. However, even though a small proportion of these bonds was present on the samples, this was independent of the CB content, as there was an overlap of the spectra on the BE region where carbon–oxygen bonds are located. Thus, the increase in the oxygen concentration in the wear track was attributed to the segregation of additives such as silica and zinc oxide, as supported by SEM and EDX analyses. This segregation was more significant for EPDM samples with 0 and 30 phr and could be related to the reduced mechanical strength and hardness, thus leading to intensive deformation of a larger volume of material in the friction zone as compared to EPDMs with higher CB content. In addition, these samples presented C=C bonds in the wear track. This effect could be explained by mechanochemical reactions resulting from non-thermally stimulated bond scission and recombination during intensive deformation of softer elastomers.

Water CA measurements confirmed the absence of polar oxygen functional groups on the surface of the wear track. No significant influence of the CB content on the wettability of EPDM was found. After friction, the water CA increased inside the wear track for all samples. This increase was especially important for the EPDM 0 phr sample. We supposed that the small variations observed in the content of additives with hydrophobic characteristics could be responsible for this variation in the water CA. Further XPS studies on the steel counter body will be performed in future in order to obtain

complementary chemical information. On the basis of these findings, we conclude that thermooxidative degradation did not occur in these EPDM samples. We suggest that the chemical modifications observed on the elastomer surfaces after the friction tests can be attributed to the mechanochemical effects, deformation and fracture of EPDM in the friction zone.

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TABLES

Table 1. Surface chemical composition (at%) of dark and bright regions in Fig. 6c obtained using energy-dispersion X-ray spectroscopy.

Element	Dark region	Bright region
C	93.48	73.56
O	4.59	12.6
Zn	0.65	11.36
Si	0.10	0.55
S	1.19	1.28

Table 2. Apparent contact angles of water on friction zone ($\theta_{fr,a}$) and untouched zone (θ_{nfr}), roughness factor (r_{fr}), calculated intrinsic contact angle ($\theta_{fr,i}$) and statistical parameters.

CB content (phr)	$\theta_{fr,a}$ (deg.)	r_{fr}	$\theta_{fr,i}$ (deg.)	SE($\theta_{fr,i}$) (deg.)	θ_{nfr} (deg.)	SE, θ_{nfr} (deg.)	p -value	$\theta_{fr,i} > \theta_{nfr}$ ($p < \alpha = 0,05$)	Power
0	119	1.654	107	4.98	81	3.9	0.013	True	0.958
30	90.7	1.102	90.6	2.11	84	2.1	0.035	True	0.589
45	105	1.207	99.3	2.46	85	1.1	0.0062	True	0.999
60	106	1.129	104	4.39	84	2.9	0.0096	True	0.954

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Fig. 1. (a) Scheme of the roller-on-plane (ROP) tribotest device.

Fig. 2. Evolution of the steady state coefficient of friction (COF) and the loss volume of EPDM elastomers as a function of the carbon black content (phr: parts per hundred parts of rubber).

Fig. 3. SEM images of the surfaces of friction zones of EPDM at 1400× magnification (a–d) and 7000× magnification (e–h). EPDM composition: a and e 0 phr; b and f 30 phr; c and g 45 phr; d and h 60 phr.

Fig. 4. Surface composition of EPDMs with different carbon black contents obtained using XPS analysis: (left hand side) outside and (right hand side) inside the wear track. Surfaces were ion sputtered before measurements to remove the air-borne surface contaminants.

Fig. 5. O 1s and C 1s core level spectra out of (a and b) and in (c and d) the wear track of the EPDM samples. Inset in (b) represents the fitting of the EPDM 0 phr sample.

Fig. 6. SEM images of the friction zone of unfilled EPDM along the sliding direction (from top to bottom). Dashed lines show the limits of the friction zone.

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FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

FIGURE 6

